

Imaging exams from a European cohort of Neuroblastoma patients. In a subcohort of patients, the annotation of the primary tumor, manually delineated by experienced radiologists is included.

ID: a3a388f6-1aa4-4a8e-8444-1a6f1e1df68d

URL: <https://eucaim-node.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/a3a388f6-1aa4-4a8e-8444-1a6f1e1df68d/details>

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Studies count: 711

Subjects count: 259

Age range: Between 0 years and 15 years

Sex: Male, Female, Undifferentiated, Unkown

Body part(s): ABDOMEN, CHEST, WHOLEBODY, OTHER, HEAD, LIVER, SPINE, ABDOMENPELVIS, TSPINE, NECK, BRAIN, PELVIS, HEART, BONE, LSPINE, S2 ESTATICA DUAL, CHESTABDOMEN, KNEE, SKULL, URINARYTRACT, GU MIBG, OPTIC CANAL, PANCREAS, TOTAL BODY, HIP, RM ABDOMEN Y_O, ORBIT, TORAX SIN, TUMOR, TORAX, GU TB MIBG I123, SZINTI MIBG, UTERUSFALLOPIAN, SMALLINTESTINE, PROSTATE, CERVICAL SPINE, SHOULDER, TOTALSPINE, TORACICO, 24H, Unknown

Modality: MR, CT, NM, PT, OT